

Lithuania | One Health Surveillance | *Foodborne diseases*

Background & objectives

- Review the legislation, data and information published on the websites of stakeholders related to foodborne diseases
- Improve the collaboration and data related to foodborne diseases sharing between different stakeholders
- Improve public tools about foodborne diseases and prevention
- Strengthen the core capacities of specialists involved in foodborne diseases

Outcomes & Impact

- A comprehensive analysis of the foodborne disease's surveillance data published on the websites NVSC has been carried out
- NVSC started to use a data protocol that includes data on identified and laboratory-confirmed individual and familial cases of salmonellosis related to food handling entities or retail outlet. This is visualized [here](#)
- An algorithm for surveillance of foodborne diseases has been developed, including outbreaks

Lessons learned

- The pilot study helped strengthen the surveillance of infectious diseases at an inter-institutional level by improving the cooperation of NVSC with the SFVS on the epidemiological surveillance of salmonellosis
- Using the information provided by the SFVS, it was possible to identify sources of more salmonellosis outbreaks that spread through food suppliers and supermarkets

Core messages

- Organize periodic meetings to discuss ongoing and planned activities
- Accurately define the data required for surveillance across sectors
- A One Health data sharing agreement needs to be put in place

